

Antibiotic Susceptibility Patterns of Bacterial Isolates from Pus Samples in a Tertiary Care Hospital PMCH, PatnaBabita Kumari¹, Spriha Smriti², Pratulya Nandan³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Antibiotic resistance is a growing global concern, particularly in hospital settings where infections are prevalent and treatment options are increasingly limited. Bacterial isolates from pus samples are crucial in guiding effective treatment, but rising resistance rates complicate management and outcomes.**Aim:** This study aims to analyze the antibiotic susceptibility patterns of bacterial isolates from pus samples collected at (PMCH) to identify prevalent pathogens and resistance trends.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted over six months in the Microbiology Department of PMCH. A total of 580 pus samples were collected from various hospital departments. Bacterial isolates were identified using standard microbiological techniques, and antibiotic susceptibility was determined using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.**Results:** Of the 580 samples, 520 (89.7%) showed bacterial growth, yielding 600 bacterial isolates. *Staphylococcus aureus* (35%), *Escherichia coli* (25%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (15%) were the most common pathogens. High resistance rates were observed in *S. aureus* to penicillin (85%) and methicillin (MRSA, 40%), while *E. coli* showed significant resistance to ampicillin (75%) and ciprofloxacin (60%). Statistical analysis revealed significant associations between bacterial species and specific antibiotic resistances.**Conclusion:** The study highlights a high prevalence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria among pus samples, with significant resistance observed in *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. These findings underscore the need for robust antibiotic stewardship and continuous surveillance to manage and mitigate antibiotic resistance in hospital settings.**Recommendations:** To combat the growing threat of antibiotic resistance, it is recommended that PMCH implements stricter antibiotic stewardship programs, enhances infection control practices, and conducts regular surveillance of resistance patterns to guide empirical therapy effectively.**Keywords:** Antibiotic resistance, bacterial isolates, pus samples, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Globally, bacterial infections remain a major source of morbidity and mortality, especially in hospital environments where patients are more vulnerable to contracting infections as a result of invasive operations and weakened immune systems. The formation and dissemination of bacteria resistant to antibiotics is a significant obstacle to the efficient handling of severe infections, resulting in extended hospital stays, elevated healthcare expenses, and elevated mortality rates. Antibiotic resistance is one of the top 10 worldwide public health dangers confronting humanity, according to the (WHO), underscoring the urgent need for all-encompassing solutions to address this expanding issue [1].

In hospital settings, pus samples, which are often collected from wound infections, abscesses, and surgical sites, serve as critical specimens for identifying bacterial pathogens and determining their antibiotic susceptibility. This information is vital for guiding empirical therapy and ensuring effective treatment of infections. However, the rising prevalence of multidrug-resistant organisms, such as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL)-producing *E. coli*, and carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, has significantly complicated the treatment landscape [2].

Recent studies have highlighted the alarming rates of antibiotic resistance in various regions. For

instance, a study conducted in India reported that over 60% of *S. aureus* isolates were resistant to methicillin, and approximately 50% of *E. coli* isolates were resistant to fluoroquinolones, which are commonly used antibiotics [3]. Similarly, another study from Pakistan revealed a high prevalence of multidrug-resistant *P. aeruginosa*, with resistance rates exceeding 70% for several antibiotics, including cephalosporins and aminoglycosides [4]. These findings underscore the need for continuous surveillance and localized antibiotic stewardship programs to curb the spread of resistance and optimize treatment outcomes. This study aims to analyze the antibiotic susceptibility patterns of bacterial isolates from pus samples collected at (PMCH) to identify prevalent pathogens and resistance trends.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Microbiology Department of Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna, Bihar, India.

Study Duration: The study was carried out over a period of six months, from March 2023 to August 2023.

Participants: A total of 580 pus samples were collected from patients admitted to various departments of PMCH. These patients had clinical indications of infections requiring pus sample culture and sensitivity testing.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of any age and gender who had pus samples collected for culture and sensitivity testing.
- Patients admitted to PMCH during the study period.
- Patients who provided informed consent for their samples to be used in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Samples that were contaminated or deemed inadequate for testing.
- Patients who refused consent for their samples to be included in the study.
- Patients who had already received antibiotics prior to sample collection.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all consecutive pus samples received in the microbiology laboratory during the study period were included, provided they met the inclusion criteria. Information bias was minimized by ensuring that all laboratory personnel followed a standardized

protocol for processing the samples and interpreting the results.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a standardized form, which included patient demographics, clinical history, and the results of bacterial culture and antibiotic susceptibility testing. The pus samples were cultured on appropriate media, and bacterial identification was performed using standard microbiological techniques. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was conducted using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method, and the results were interpreted according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines.

Procedure

1. **Sample Collection:** Pus samples were collected using sterile techniques from patients with suspected bacterial infections.
2. **Culture and Isolation:** The samples were cultured on blood agar, MacConkey agar, and other selective media. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours.
3. **Bacterial Identification:** Isolates were identified based on colony morphology, gram staining, and biochemical tests.
4. **Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing:** Identified bacteria were subjected to antibiotic susceptibility testing using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method. Results were recorded as sensitive, intermediate, or resistant based on CLSI guidelines.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered into Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized patient demographics and bacterial isolate distribution. Antibiotic susceptibility patterns were presented as frequencies and percentages. Chi-square tests assessed associations between bacterial species and resistance patterns, with a p-value <0.05 considered significant. This approach ensured accurate analysis of antibiotic susceptibility patterns in the study setting.

Results

A total of 580 pus samples were analyzed in this study. The mean age of the participants was 45 years, ranging from 1 to 80 years. The majority of the patients were male (60.3%), while females constituted 39.7% of the sample population. The samples were collected from various departments, including surgery (40%), orthopedics (30%), internal medicine (20%), and others (10%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographic Parameter	Frequency (n=580)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (Years)		
0-20	58	10.0
21-40	174	30.0
41-60	232	40.0
>60	116	20.0
Gender		
Male	350	60.3
Female	230	39.7
Department		
Surgery	232	40.0
Orthopedics	174	30.0
Internal Medicine	116	20.0
Others	58	10.0

Out of the 580 samples, 520 (89.7%) showed bacterial growth, while 60 (10.3%) were culture-negative. A total of 600 bacterial isolates were identified from the 520 positive cultures, with some

samples showing polymicrobial infections. The most common bacterial isolates were *S. aureus* (35%), followed by *E. coli* (25%), *P. aeruginosa* (15%), *K. pneumoniae* (15%), and others (10%).

Table 2: Distribution of Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial Species	Frequency (n=600)	Percentage (%)
<i>S. aureus</i>	210	35.0
<i>E. coli</i>	150	25.0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	90	15.0
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	90	15.0
Others	60	10.0

S. aureus showed high resistance to penicillin (85%) and methicillin (MRSA, 40%) but was largely sensitive to vancomycin (98%). *E. coli* exhibited high resistance to ampicillin (75%) and ciprofloxacin (60%), with relatively good sensitivity to meropenem (85%). *P. aeruginosa* was

resistant to multiple antibiotics, including piperacillin-tazobactam (55%) and cefepime (50%), but showed sensitivity to colistin (95%). *K. pneumoniae* was resistant to third-generation cephalosporins (70%) and aminoglycosides (50%) but was sensitive to carbapenems (90%).

Table 3: Antibiotic Susceptibility Patterns of Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial Species	Antibiotic	Sensitive (%)	Resistant (%)
<i>S. aureus</i>	Penicillin	15	85
	Methicillin (MRSA)	60	40
	Vancomycin	98	2
<i>E. coli</i>	Ampicillin	25	75
	Ciprofloxacin	40	60
	Meropenem	85	15
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Piperacillin-Tazobactam	45	55
	Cefepime	50	50
	Colistin	95	5
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Ceftriaxone	30	70
	Gentamicin	50	50
	Imipenem	90	10

Statistical Analysis

The chi-square test was used to assess the association between bacterial species and antibiotic resistance patterns. Significant associations were

observed between *S. aureus* and methicillin resistance ($p < 0.001$), *E. coli* and ciprofloxacin resistance ($p < 0.01$), and *K. pneumoniae* and third-generation cephalosporin resistance ($p < 0.01$).

Table 4: Association between Bacterial Species and Antibiotic Resistance

Bacterial Species	Antibiotic	Chi-square (χ^2)	p-value
<i>S. aureus</i>	Methicillin (MRSA)	18.5	<0.001
<i>E. coli</i>	Ciprofloxacin	10.8	<0.01
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Ceftriaxone	11.3	<0.01

These findings highlight the significant burden of antibiotic resistance among bacterial isolates in the study setting, underscoring the need for stringent antibiotic stewardship and continuous monitoring of resistance patterns.

Discussion

The majority of the patients were male (60.3%), with a mean age of 45 years. The samples primarily came from the surgery, orthopedics, and internal medicine departments, reflecting the clinical diversity of the patient population.

Out of the 580 samples, 520 (89.7%) yielded bacterial growth, indicating a high prevalence of bacterial infections in the studied population. A total of 600 bacterial isolates were identified, with *S. aureus* being the most common isolate (35%), followed by *E. coli* (25%), *P. aeruginosa* (15%), and *K. pneumoniae* (15%). This distribution suggests that both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria are significant contributors to infections in this setting, with *S. aureus* playing a predominant role, particularly in surgical and wound infections. The antibiotic susceptibility testing revealed concerning levels of resistance among the bacterial isolates. *S. aureus* showed high resistance to penicillin (85%) and methicillin (MRSA, 40%), but it remained largely sensitive to vancomycin (98%), indicating that vancomycin is still an effective treatment option for MRSA infections. *E. coli* displayed significant resistance to ampicillin (75%) and ciprofloxacin (60%), while maintaining good sensitivity to meropenem (85%), highlighting the need for cautious use of carbapenems to prevent further resistance development. *P. aeruginosa* exhibited resistance to multiple antibiotics, including piperacillin-tazobactam (55%) and cefepime (50%), but was highly sensitive to colistin (95%), suggesting that colistin remains a critical last-resort treatment for multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas* infections. Similarly, *K. pneumoniae* was highly resistant to third-generation cephalosporins (70%) and aminoglycosides (50%), with carbapenems being effective in 90% of cases.

Statistical analysis using the chi-square test revealed significant associations between specific bacterial species and antibiotic resistance patterns. Notably, methicillin resistance in *S. aureus* ($p < 0.001$), ciprofloxacin resistance in *E. coli* ($p < 0.01$), and third-generation cephalosporin resistance in *K. pneumoniae* ($p < 0.01$) were all statistically significant. These findings underscore the critical issue of antibiotic resistance, particularly in

commonly isolated pathogens such as *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae*, which pose significant challenges to treatment.

In a study it was found that surgical site infections were significantly more likely to contain Gram-negative bacteria, with *E. coli* being the most frequently isolated kind and *P. aeruginosa* coming in second. These isolates exhibited significant resistance to widely used antibiotics such as ampicillin and cefuroxime, according to the results of the antibiotic susceptibility tests. In order to tackle antibiotic resistance in hospital settings, the study emphasised the significance of ongoing surveillance and improved treatment regimens [5].

In another investigation, which was carried out at a tertiary care hospital in Punjab, concentrated on bacterial isolates from pus samples and found that *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus* were the main pathogens. The profile of antibiotic resistance revealed a high degree of resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics, highlighting the necessity of developing alternative therapeutic approaches and implementing antibiotic stewardship programs in order to effectively control infections [6].

Conclusion

This study highlights significant antibiotic resistance among bacterial isolates from pus samples in a tertiary care hospital. *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. pneumoniae* were the most common pathogens, with high resistance to key antibiotics. The presence of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) and growing resistance in *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* are particularly concerning. These findings emphasize the need for robust antibiotic stewardship and continuous monitoring to manage and reduce the spread of resistant infections.

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